

ISic1432

I.Sicily inscription 1432

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific; signature
(?)

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Himera

Place of origin (modern)

Imera

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 2752

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐκλεί[δεως]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285049

EDCS 64900779

PHI 175611

Bibliography

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Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 12 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 17

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